

SOP for the Measurement of Sweetness (Total Soluble Solids) in Fresh and Boiled Plantain using a Refractometer

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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SOP: Colour Measurement in Fresh and Boiled Plantain using a Chromameter

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ABSTRACT

The taste of plantain fruits is highly influenced by the amount of soluble solids. Total soluble solids is the amounts of dissolved solids (mostly sugar) in a food sample. It can be determined with the help of a Refractometer which is an optical instrument that can deduce the amounts of these solids in a liquid sample of the food stuff to be assayed. It functions based on the principle of light refraction which is the bending of light as it passes from one medium to another due to difference in density. In this case, the difference in density is created by the concentration of dissolved solids in the sample giving higher refractive index for samples with high sugar contents. This parameter which determines plantain fruits sweetness is crucial as it helps in the determination of ripening stages in fruits. It is also distinctive of the flavour of plantain fruits during ripening. Aside ripening stage that makes it content to vary from one stage to another, cooking modes greatly influence the sweetness of these fruits. As such, assessing the soluble solids of plantain fruits at different ripening stages and mode of cooking gives us an insight of the best mode to be used for cooking as well as the appropriate ripening stage.

Keywords: Total soluble content, Refractive Index, Ripening stage, Cooking modes, Refractometer

1 SCOPE AND APPLICATION

Total soluble solids (TSS) is an important parameter for fruit quality. TSS represents the amount of soluble solids in the sample. The TSS value affects the flavour of the fruit as it indicates its sweetness level. In most plantain and banana fruits, sugar forms the main component of soluble solids (Dadzie and Orchard, 1997). TSS is dominated by total sugars and a small number of soluble proteins, amino acids and other organic substances (Bexiga *et al.*, 2017). The determination of total soluble solids is usually performed by a destructive method that requires laboratory testing. In addition, this method damages the fruit. Destructive methods of TSS measurement are usually done using refractometers. Sweetness measurement helps in determining the ripeness of plantains. As plantains ripen, starches convert to sugars, increasing sweetness. This process is crucial for farmers and distributors to decide the optimal harvest time.

2 REFERENCES

Bexiga, F., Rodrigues, D., Guerra, R., Brázio, A., Balegas, T., Cavaco, A. M., Antunes, M. D., & de Oliveira J. V. (2017). *Postharvest Biol. Technol.* 132 23-30.

Dadzie, B.K., & Orchard J.E., (1997). *Routine postharvest screening of banana and plantain hybrids: criteria and methods*, INIBAP, Techn. Guidel. 2, Montpellier, France, 1997, 63p

3 PRINCIPLE

Refractometers measure the total soluble solids (TSS) concentration based on the principle of refraction of light. When light travels from one medium to another at a certain angle, it bends or refracts. Refraction occurs because light travels at slightly different speeds in different media, the extent of which is proportional to the density of the solution or the concentration of soluble solids. The refractive index of a medium is defined as the ratio of the sine of the angle of incidence to the sine of the angle of refraction when a monochromatic beam of light is refracted into the medium from a vacuum (or, to a very close approximation, from air). In a Brix refractometer, the refractive index is calibrated into °Brix readings. Changes in direction of a light beam passing through the solution correlate to the amount of dissolved solids in the solution. Basically, the higher the level of soluble solids in the solution, the greater the bending of the light beam as observed in (Fig1).

Figure 1: Illustration of how the Refractometer works

4 REAGENTS

No reagent used except the solvent water

5 APPARATUS

Table 1: Equipments used ant the functions

Materials	Image
<p>Stainless steel knife</p> <p>The stainless-steel knife is carbon steel with added chromium to resist corrosion and other elements which increase performance levels.</p>	
<p>Chemical balance and disposable cup</p> <p>For weighing the required 30g for subsequent blending</p>	
<p>Cooking pots</p> <p>The pot is stainless with an advantage of heating up rapidly during cooking</p>	
<p>Stainless spoon</p> <p>Cooking spoon with rubber handle(insulator) used during plantain boiling</p>	

<p>Tray</p> <p>To carry raw plantain fruits after washing and boiled fruits from fire to weighing site</p>	
<p>Blender (Silver crest model)</p> <p>For grinding of both raw and boiled fruits to have the plantain fruit solution</p>	
<p>Measuring cylinder</p> <p>Measuring the volume of water required for the blending process</p>	
<p>Beaker</p> <p>For holding the weighed plantain cossettes and water as well the sample after grinding</p>	
<p>Small pipette</p> <p>For taking small amounts of samples for the refractometer</p>	
<p>Refractometer</p> <p>For reading the refractive index (°Brix) of the sample</p>	

6 PROCEDURE

To calibrate the refractometer

- Close the prism lid, check that the water film contains no air bubbles, then point the refractometer towards a light source. You will see blue band field in the viewfinder, containing a vertical scale with 0.2°B graduations. When there is liquid on the prism, the field is divided into a light and a blue part. The point at which the dividing line between these two parts crosses the vertical scale gives the measurement in °Brix or the

estimated TSS content. With distilled water, this measurement should be 0.5°B. After calibrating the refractometer with distilled water, it is important to check its accuracy with freshly prepared sucrose solutions of known concentration, for example 12% sucrose by weight/vol. (i.e 12 g of sucrose in 88 ml of distilled water).

If the point of intersection between the demarcation line and the refractometer scale is not distinct, this may be due to the presence of large air bubbles in the film of the juice or sample (a sufficient quantity of juice should be poured on it to ensure that the prism surface is well covered) and the moisture penetrating the refractometer's optical system (the equipment should then be dried at 30-40°C). Between measurements, the surface of the refractometer prism should be systematically and carefully wiped with soft tissue paper. After use, wash the prism in distilled water, dry it carefully with soft tissue paper and store it in a safe place until you are ready to use it again.

Measurement of the refractive index of pulp juice (grind sample) using a refractometer

The plantain bunch was harvested at physiological maturity stage (i.e appearance of a ripe fruit either on the first hand, or the second hand of the bunch) early in the morning. The bunch was carried to the laboratory. The fruits from the second and third hands were removed and washed with running water.

The refractive index (or soluble solids content) of the pulp of dessert bananas, cooking bananas and plantains is measured as follows:

- ✓ In a kitchen blender, grind 30 g of pulps cossettes (taken from the cross-section of the fruit) in 90 ml of distilled water for 2 minutes, then let it stand for 1min-3min (depending on whether the sample is raw or boiled, liquid or pasty) or filter (using filter paper Whatman 4, for example) ;
- ✓ Place a single drop of the filtrate on the refractometer prism (figure 1 shows a HUMEAU ATC hand-held refractometer), measuring in Brix degrees from 0 to 10°B at 20°C);
 - ✓ Point the refractometer at a light source and read the total soluble solid content;
 - ✓ Multiply the recorded value by three (because the initial pulp sample was diluted in three times the volume of distilled water).
 - ✓ Repeat this process twice to obtain 3 data sets

Note: This process was done for three fruits per bunch.

Figure 2: Workflow for determining total soluble of plantain fruits using refractometer.

7 EXPRESSION OF RESULTS

The total soluble solid (TSS) is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{TSS (°Brix)} = 3 \times \text{RI} - 0,8$$

"3 represent the dilution factor which is 3 like in this case."

Below is a sample table showing how the values read, calculated and been recorded (fresh and boiled pulps)

Table 2: Sample representation of calculated TSS

Cultivar	0(raw)	10	20	30	40	50	60
CARBAP K74	0,20	18,80	17,60	18,20	18,20	18,80	18,20
Batard	-0,20	7,40	19,40	21,20	19,00	18,80	19,00

8 CRITICAL POINTS OR NOTE ON THE PROCEDURE

- The temperature of the cooked sample (cooling after cooking to an average of 50°C) must be respected before grinding as it may affect the measurement of the soluble dry solids;
- Ensure that the sample has been well ground to facilitate extraction and reading;
- Ensure the viewing of the refractometer is done under a bright light source;
- Always multiply the value by the dilution factor;
- Minimize as much as possible the time between which the blended sample stays in the beaker before reading the refractive index;

Put just a drop on the refractometer to get a clear and good reading.